

“Relationship Between Oral Health Status and Glycemic Control Among Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus Patients Residing In An Urban Localaity of Mysuru Karnataka”

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Abstract

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is considered as a heterogeneous group of disorders that are caused by a relative or absolute insulin deficiency which further causes abnormalities in carbohydrate, protein and lipid metabolism. The correlation between systemic and oral symptoms of diabetes will provide the means for proper and early diagnosis and prior treatment. Hence a cross sectional study was conducted to investigate the relationship between oral health status and glycemic control among type –2 diabetes mellitus patients residing in an urban locality of mysuru. The study involved a total population of 225 adults with 138(61.33%) males and 87(38.67%) females of the age group between between 25-80 years..Mean age of the population was 47.19 ± 12.62 . The peak prevalence of DM was in the group aged 55-64.Majority of the participants, 144(64%) participants were having disease since 1 to 3 years. 11(4.89%) have had the diseases for longest duration of equal to or more than 10 years. Prevalence of periodontal disease among study population was 25.16% for maxillary and 26.41% for mandibular. 70.33% were in the controlled diabetes group and 29.67% in uncontrolled group. There was no difference in the mean DMFT score of both the group. The prevalence of periodontal disease was found to be more in uncontrolled diabetes group. There is clear correlated evidence between diabetic patients and periodontal diseases. Subjects with diabetes mellitus and with high blood glucose levels showed severe periodontal conditions. There is a need for the collaboration of physicians and dental team in the management of diabetic patients which can improve the oral health condition and overall quality of life.

Key words: Diabetes Mellitus, Oral Health, DMFT Scores, Periodontal Diseases

Introduction

Diabetes is considered as a heterogeneous group of disorders that are caused by a relative or absolute insulin deficiency which further causes abnormalities in carbohydrate, protein and lipid metabolism¹. Diabetes has been known to humankind for about centuries. WHO within the year 1980 has revealed its 1st of the numerous wide accepted versions for the classification of diabetes² and then it published the updated version in the year 1985³. This system of classifications has included the two major classes of diabetes:

- Insulin Dependent Diabetes Mellitus (IDDM), Or Type 1 and
- Non-Insulin Dependent Diabetes Mellitus (NIDDM), or Type 2.

It can be broadly classified into four broad categories four broad classes in line with its signs and symptoms it shows.

- Type 1
- Type 2
- Gestational Diabetes that occur exclusively in pregnant women and
- Other specific types of diabetes In addition, there are specific types of diabetes, including defects in pancreatic beta cells and insulin resistance, as well as diseases of the

exocrine pancreas, and endocrino pathies and drug-induced diabetes. s well as the drug-induced types of diabetes.⁴

While caring for the other problems associated with the Diabetes Mellitus the oral cavity is often overlooked. This correlation between systemic and oral symptoms will provide the means for proper and early diagnosis and prior treatment. Hence this study will be undertaken to find out the relationship between oral health status and glycemic control among diabetics residing in an urban area of Mysuru, Karnataka.

Objective

- To assess Oral health status among diabetic patients attending urban primary health centre.
- To find out the relation between oral health status and glycemic control and study subjects

Methodology

A cross sectional study was conducted on

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the known diabetic patients visiting the urban primary health centre, JSS, Medar's block and UPHC Bannimantap attached to Department of Community Medicine, JSS Medical College, Mysuru over the time period of 6 months i.e from January 2021- June 2021 following the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion criteria

· Subjects diagnosed to have Type 2 Diabetes mellitus and on treatment for at least one year and consenting to participate in the study.

- Subjects more than 18 years of age
- Subjects who did not had any other medical conditions affecting the oral health.
- Exclusion criteria:
 - Those Diabetics with cognitive dysfunctions and not able to understand the verbal commands will be excluded.
 - Those who did not cooperate for the study.
 - Those with a presence of severe neuro degenerative disease

Survey Instrument

1. Pre tested proforma was used to assess Socio demographic characteristics of study subjects like age, gender, education, occupation, income, marital status, socioeconomic status etc

2. Questionnaire was used to get Details on Diabetes Mellitus like, age of onset, duration, , medications, frequency of follow up, medication history , regularity of treatment etc Glycated Hemoglobin (HbA1c) was collected from most recent record (maximum three months) of the study subject. HbA1c tests measures the blood sugar level attached with the hemoglobin. the value for HbA1c for known diabetic is $\geq 48\text{mmol/mol}$ or $\geq 6.5\%$.

1. Oral health status: WHO oral health status assessment form for adults -2013 was used for assessing the oral health status and the the oral cavity type III clinical examination was carried out to confirm the findings.

Statistical Analysis: All the data collected were put in a Microsoft excel sheet. Basic calculations were done in the same. The continuous data were summarized as Mean \pm SD. The Chi-square test was used to test the distribution among variables. P-value of < 0.05 was taken as statistically significant. The analysis was done using SPSS version 18.

Results and Discussion

Out of 225 there were 138(61.33%) males and 87(38.67%) females.(FIGURE 1) the sample size in this study is similar to the one taken by Manjunath , P Puranik and S S Hiremath⁵. Majority of the population were in the age group of 41-50 Mean age of the population was 47.19 ± 12.62 . The peak prevalence of DM was in the group aged 55-64. (TABLE 1. The studies done on 3314 subjects aged 20 and above by A Rama chandran et al.⁶ showed mean the peak prevalence 55-64 Years. Highest numbers of the population in the study group were graduate i.e. 61 (27.11%). (FIGURE 2) our study showed that the educational level had no impact on glycemic control, which is consistent with some studies^{7,8} but not with others⁹. In a study by Mohamed HG et. al,¹⁰ it was showed that a total of 31.2% of the cases had experience the diagnosis of Diabetes mellitus for more than 10 years whereas in our study 11(4.89%) have had the disease for longest duration of equal to or more than 10 years. (TABLE2) When observing the age of onset for diabetes mellitus 90(40%) had got this disease before they

could reach forty years of age. According to the results of the national urban diabetes survey in India, more than half of diabetic patients were diagnosed before the age of ¹¹. The age of onset for the disease diagnosis has its own limitations as the onset age tells us about the start of the disease and does not give any information about the actual existence of the disease. Patient could have had it long before the diagnosis. 139(61.78%) in our study reported the history of diabetes mellitus in the family, another similar history showed around half of the sample had family history.¹²The last physical exam taken by majority of the population was one week before the data collection i.e. 63.66%, the eye examination is taken long way back by 72.44% and the dental exam was taken 1 to 3 months back by 79.55% of sample population. (TABLE 3) The time of the examination is significant to the type of examination taken. The chi-square value was 218.3909. At p-value is < 0.00001 . The result is found to be significant. According to the National Survey of People with Diabetes in Europe when the samples were told to inform about the times in the last 12 months they had a general body check-up. Forty three percent answered to 2 times, thirty four answered for 1, twenty percent replied about 3 or more times and three percent had not taken any check up in the last 12 months. For eye checkup Four fifths of respondents had taken a photograph for the back of the eyes (retinography). Test is taken more by Type 2 Type than type 1 (81% and 75% respectively). This difference in the eye examination could be due the presence of health coverage plans in developed cities like Europe. in India people tend to doctors only in need, the general timely checkup is still not practiced by majority of the Indians , financial burden and carelessness towards health being the top reason for the same.¹³ In our study 10.2% sample were under the category of smokers and 5.7% consumed alcohol. (FIGURE 3)

The mean DMFT score for our participants came up to 0.54 which is similar to the value obtained by Dr. Manjunath et al.⁵ and it was way lesser then the DMFT score given by Aggnur, et al.¹⁴ which was 5.02.. In the study by Lydia M.¹⁵ Mean caries indexes for permanent teeth was 1.43 in case group and 0.56 for controls. (TABLE 4) The bleeding was present in 25.16% of maxillary teeth and 26.41% of mandibular teeth which is much lesser to the results shown by Safia Abidi about 74.2% had inflamed, swollen or bleeding present. Another study was conducted in Ethiopia in which Bahru and Abdu found 65.7% diabetic patients had bleeding present.^{16,17} (TABLE 5) 64(70.33%) had HbA1c less than 7% hence they were taken as controlled diabetic group. 27(29.67%) had value more than or equal to 7% 200 mg/dl and hence those were kept in uncontrolled diabetic group. Male predominance is seen in both the controlled and uncontrolled group. There was no difference in the mean DMFT score of both the group. there was not much difference in the decayed cases, which is in contrast to the results published by JV Bharateesh which states the prevalence of dental caries was comparatively more in uncontrolled diabetic group (32.3%) than in controlled diabetic group (13.6%). (TABLE 6) Out of total 319 teeth in the controlled group with presence of pocket 156 (48.90%) had pocket depth of 4-5mm and 163(51.10%) had value $\geq 6\text{mm}$. out of 490 teeth in uncontrolled group a significantly high number 282 (57.55%) had pocket depth between 4-5mm and 208(42.45%) had value $\geq 6\text{mm}$. periodontal disease prevalence was found more in uncontrolled diabetes group. similar results have been

reported in other other studies by JV Bharateesh¹⁷, A Rama chandran⁶, Dr. Manjunath⁵, and S Geetha¹⁸. according to a literature review 44 of 48 (37 cross-sectional and 7 cohort) the observational studies research has reported and has provided supportive evidence in support of diabetes affecting the periodontal condition¹⁹

Figures & Tables

Figure 1: Distribution of Study Subjects Bases on Gender

Age Groups (Years)	Number	Percentage
18-30	18	8
31-40	54	24
41-50	60	26.67
51-60	55	24.44
>61 and above	38	16.89
TOTAL	225	100

Table 1: Distribution of Study Subjects Based on Age

Figure 2: Distribution of Study Subjects Bases on Education

Years of Diabetic Duration (years)	Number	Percentage
1-3	144	64.0
4-6	60	26.67
7-9	10	4.44
>=10	11	4.89
Total	225	100

Table 2: Distribution of Study Subjects Based on Diabetes Duration

Last Examination	Physical	Eye	Dental
One Week Before Data Collection	45 (20%)	15 (6.67%)	11 (4.89%)
One Month Before Data Collection	143 (63.66%)	47 (20.89%)	35 (15.56)
1 Month To 3 Months Before Data Collection	37 (16.44%)	163 (72.44%)	179 (79.55)
	225 (100%)	225 (100%)	225 (100%)

The chi-square statistic is 218.3909. The p-value is < 0.00001. The result is significant at p < .05.

Table 3: Distribution of Study Subjects Based on patient's Last Examination

Figure 3: Distribution of Study Subjects Based on smoke And Alcohol Consumption

Mean Dmft Calculation	Maxillary		Mandibular		Total	Mean Calculation	Mean
	Crown	Root	Crown	Root			
Decayed	906	318	951	326	2501	2501/14400	0.173681
Missing	402	402	803	402	2009	2009/14400	0.139514
Filled	1243	638	765	538	3184	3184/14400	0.221111
DMFT	2551	1358	2519	1266	7694	7694/14400	0.534306
Total Frequency	36001	36002	36003	36004	14400		

1. maxillary crown 225*16= 3600, 2. maxillary root 225* 16 =3600, 3.mandibular crown 225*16= 3600, 4.mandibular root 225*16= 3600

Table 4: Mean Calculation For Decayed Missing Filled Teeth (dmft)

Bleeding Score Calculation	Cpi Bleeding Score			
	Maxillary		Mandibular	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Absence Of Condition	1028	28.56	735	20.41
Presence Of Condition	906	25.16	951	26.41
Tooth Excluded	1169	32.4	1032	28.63
Tooth Not Present	497	13.81	882	24.5
Total	36001	100	36002	100

1. maxillary teeth 225*16= 3600, 2. mandibular teeth 225*16=3600, 3

Table 5: Description of Bleeding Score For Coomunity Periodontal Index (cpi)

Total	Controlled	Uncontrolled	P
Decayed	0.25 ±.03	0.26 ±.03	0.0001
Missing	0.18 ±.03	0.18 ±.03	1.0000
Filled	0.16 ±.03	0.17 ±.03	0.0001
DMFT	0.60±.09	0.60±.09	1.0000
Total Frequency	2048	864	

Table 6: Comparison of Mean Dmft Between Controlled And Uncontrolled Diabetics

Conclusion

There was no difference in the mean DMFT score of both the group. Gingival Bleeding and pocket depth of more than or equal to 4mm was observed more in uncontrolled diabetes group. There is clear correlated evidence between diabetic patients and periodontal diseases. The prevalence of periodontal disease was found to be more in uncontrolled diabetes group.

Recommendations

- Team collaboration is recommended between general physician and practicing dental surgeons to screen all the diabetics for periodontal diseases and provide proper care
- Awareness camps are needed for the combined knowledge of diabetes and oral health covering the anterior areas to reach the unreached.
- Planning and implementation of oral health programs are recommended.

Limitations

- The study is carried out in a small population of 225 which is a relatively small to make generalized conclusion.
- Long term further study is needed to confirm these findings
- Method adopted was cross sectional study but a longitudinal or cohort studies will be advantageous to understand magnitude, trends or further effects of diabetes on oral and general health.

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